

FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF WOOD FILLED POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Current issues on composite materials have been discussed and published in many literatures, including some virtuous inventions on improvement of mechanical properties and hybridizing conventional composites with bio-based fillers. This work includes the development of woods as reinforcing fillers for polymeric matrix to form an environmentally friendly composite material, i.e. wood-plastic composites (WPCs). Appropriate amount of fillers and the compatibility of woods with the hydrophobic polymer are among the issues that have been discussed as the significant factors for improving the properties of the WPCs material. Thus, in this study, different amount of wood fillers was employed to wood-polypropylene (PP) composites in order to clarify the relation between the amount of fillers and the fatigue properties of the WPCs material. Here, the dried WPCs pellets containing relatively higher amount of wood fillers than the polymer matrix were mixed with the dried PP pellets through an extrusion process and molded by the injection molding machine. From the tensile test results, it was understood that the tensile properties of the plain PP was proportionally enhanced by increasing the weight fraction of the wood fillers. A similar result was obtained from fatigue test, which suggested that the increase in weight fraction of woods enhanced the fatigue properties of the WPCs material. The improvement of both properties was estimated due to the good interfacial adhesion of matrix-fillers which was assisted by the addition of the coupling agent. Further analysis on fracture surface has been carried out and the relation between microscopic fracture and the fatigue behavior will be further discussed in this study.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have become an appropriate alternative medium that can be used instead of the conventional single material in many industries. These are applied as the primary structural material for many sport's equipments such as tennis racket, golf shaft, bicycle frame and kayaks, as well as for automotives and architecture applications. This is because composite materials offer wide range of advantageous such as high durability, light weight, high stiffness and low maintenance. Moreover, the composite properties can be directed to the desired properties that suit the application by selecting two or more appropriate constituents. This benefit matches to the manufacturers who desire the reduced production cost besides excellent properties of the materials, and in particular reduction of the environmental impact.

These days, the environmental aspect turns to a global concern that needs to be considered in most applications. The usage of petroleum-derived materials that is commonly difficult to recycle, affects

the environment. Moreover, less energy efficiency due to the usage of single conventional materials causes more wastage and also results in an environmental problem. Taking an advantage from the composite materials processing method, the environmentally friendly composite materials, or known as *green composites* can be produced, for example, by combining bio-based fillers with a biodegradable resin or minimizing the use of petroleum-derived materials such as polymer by incorporating the natural-based reinforcements into the polymeric matrix. Bamboo, kenaf, flax and jute are the typical natural-based fibers. They can be used either as long fibers (unidirectional fibers, woven, etc.) or short fibers (chopped fibers) as reinforcement in the polymeric resin.

Although there are many natural based resources available, wood fibers are compatible as a filler of *green composites* because of its ease of availability and low production cost. Single wood materials have been used in many products such as household articles, furniture and other interior items for centuries. However, as mentioned above, the single wood or ply-wood material can be replaced with the wood filled composite materials, which are much lighter and less cost, named wood-plastic composites (WPCs). As a kind of *green composites*, the combination of wood flour with polymeric matrices brings a new sight in wood-based application, i.e. high durability and excellent mechanical properties such as high tensile strength and stiffness [1-3]. These natural fibers play a role of transferring the load and act as a *crack-bridge* at a crack tip upon failure. In spite of that, due to the incompatibility of wood surface structure with the polymer matrix, it might be difficult to obtain the maximum performances of compounded wood flour composite materials - similar difficulties are posed by other natural based fibers in producing *green composites*. Moreover, the characteristics of wood flour are different with respect to the type of trees and harvesting time and it is easily influenced by the presence of moisture. In conjunction, from the manufacturing process up to the wearing of the WPCs product, the failure aspects are concerned by various factors, and indeed require a proper attention. Flaws on surface, improper maintenance, stress concentration are among the factors that limit WPCs life. It is important to understand those factors in order to control their life span and the remaining life, and also, these factors varies depending on the surrounding environment, material's selection and geometry, and so on.

Here, regarding the fatigue of wood based materials, the study on fatigue damage and hysteresis in wood-epoxy laminates by Hacker and Ansell [4] gives a general understanding on how importance of fatigue behavior of these materials to be analyzed before it is practically applied. Analysis on the wood laminates shows varies results regarding to the loading mode, e.g. tension-tension, compression-compression and reverse loading, which closely related with various type of applications. Bao et al. [5] compared the fatigue behavior of several types of wood composites in order to understand the allowable design stress for wood furniture application. The fatigue resistance was analyzed by applying several level of fatigue stress to each type of sample - Particleboard (PB), medium density fiberboard (MDF), oriented strand board (OSB) and hardwood plywood (PL). From the results, it is understand that all type of specimens had longer fatigue life, over 1million cycles, at stress level of 30% of average ultimate tensile strength (UTS), and the fatigue fracture takes place at stress level of 40% of UTS. However, for both study, the fatigue behavior concerning the fracture surface analysis of each loading mode, which suppose to give a significance attribute related to the failure analysis of the wood laminates composites material, were not explained. The fatigue fracture surface is believed to contribute effectively in order to understand more about the life span and the durability of the WPCs. Thus, this study aims at understanding the fatigue behavior of wood flour filled polypropylene matrix composite materials and its relation to the morphology of the fatigue fracture surface. We first tried to analyze the influences of the wood flour weight fraction. Next, the degree of wood flour dispersion on the WPCs fatigue life were clarified, and finally discussed about the fatigue fracture surface inherent in the WPCs.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

In this study, WPCs specimens with different weight fraction of wood flours were prepared by using *master-batch* pellets (composition ratio - wood particles:PP:MAPP = 70:30:2.8), produced by TOCLAS Corporation. The pellets were mixed with J107G type polypropylene, produced by Prime Polymer Co., by using a single screw extruder machine in order to gain desired weight fractions of wood flours.

2.2 Sample Preparation

In order to clarify the effect of wood flours contents on the fatigue properties, specimens with different weight fraction of wood flour were fabricated. The PP and *master-batch* pellets were first dried in convection oven (MOV-112F; Sanyo Co.) at 120°C for 5h to reduce the moisture contents. Then, the PP were added and mixed together with *master-batch* pellets, to change the wood flour weight fraction to a desired amount, i.e. 50 wt.% and 30 wt.% respectively. The mixing process was done using a single screw extruder machine (Musashino Kikai Co. Ltd.) at 190°C, with a constant screw rotation speed of 20 rpm. The mixing process was done once or twice at the same temperature and speed in order to explore an optimum dispersion of wood flours. After that, the mixture was chopped into 5mm length pellet before molded into a dumbbell shape via an injection molding machine at 200°C. As for the neat PP specimen, the dried PP pellets were directly added into the injection molding machine and molded under the same condition with wood flour filled WPCs specimens. The shape and dimension of neat PP and WPCs specimens are shown in Fig. 1. The specimens were kept for at least 24h before the mechanical test was carried out.

Fig. 1 Shape and dimension of neat PP and WPCs specimens.

2.3 Tensile and Fatigue test

A small-type desktop testing machine (LSC-1/300; JT Tohsi INC.) was used to determine the tensile properties of each type of specimen. A strain amplifier (DPM-700B; Kyowa Electronic Instruments Co. Ltd.) and a strain gauge (KFG-2N-120-C1-11; Kyowa Electronic Instrument Co. Ltd.) were used for strain measurements during the tensile test. Tensile tests were conducted at the crosshead speed of 1 mm/min up to fracture at room temperature. The number of cycles to failure of each specimen was measured through a fatigue test using an electric oil pressure servo type material testing machine (9.8kN load capacity, Servo pulser EHF-FBI-4LA; Shimadzu Corp.) at room temperature. The fatigue test was conducted at 50%–80% levels of static fracture load, obtained from the tensile test, up to fracture or achieving more than 10^6 cyclic numbers. The stress ratio used in this study was 0.1 and the frequency was set in the range of 3Hz to 5Hz, respectively.

2.4 Surface Observation

In order to understand the morphological structure of the wood flours filled polypropylene composite specimens at fracture area, the fracture surface of composite specimens from fatigue test

was observed using the scanning electron microscope (SEM). The fracture surface sample was prepared by cutting the fractured specimens into 5mm in length and the golden vapor deposition was conducted at appropriate thickness for each sample using micro-ion weld slag equipment. On the other hand, the wood flour distribution was observed from the arbitrary cross-sectional area of the specimen. The cross-sectional sample was prepared by embedded the specimen, that has been cut and polished at any cross-section area, into an epoxy-hardener solution in a silicon-case and hardened for 24h at room temperature. Then, the observation surface was ground by using a grinding machine before it was polished. Finally, before the SEM observation, the golden vapor deposition was applied at the observation surface of the sample stage. Besides SEM, the fracture surface area was also observed using the 3D Laser Measuring Microscope (LEXT OLS4000; Olympus Co.). The samples were observed at room temperature with three different objective lens, 20x, 50x and 100x, respectively.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile test

Figure 2 illustrates the stress-strain diagram of representatives for neat PP and WPCs specimens. From the tensile test result, it is understood that the tensile strength and Young's modulus of PP material improved by compounding the wood flour into the PP matrix. Table 1 shows the average value of tensile properties of neat PP, 30 wt.% and 50 wt.% of wood composition in WPCs specimens. As shown in this table, the tensile strength and Young's modulus properties increased with increasing the weight fraction of wood flours. Moreover, it is understand that, by compounding 30 wt.% of wood flour into the PP matrix, the strength and modulus of the materials showed about 22% and 75% increases, respectively, and both properties increased up to 51% and 135% for 50%WF/PP specimens, respectively.

Fig. 2 Stress-strain diagram of neat PP and WPCs specimens.

Table 1 Average value of tensile properties of neat PP and WPCs specimens.

Specimens	Tensile strength σ [MPa]	Maximum load P_{max} [N]	Young's modulus E [GPa]
Neat PP	38.2	10.0	2.00
30% WF/PP	46.5	5.89	3.49
50% WF/PP	57.7	4.94	4.70

3.2 Fatigue test

Number of cycles to failure of each specimen was obtained from the fatigue test. From this result, the durability of the material under an arbitrary load can be estimated. Figure 3 illustrates the maximum stress to the number of cycles, so-called ‘S-N curves’, for neat PP specimen and WF/PP specimens with different wood flour weight percentages. As compared to neat PP specimen, the WF/PP specimens tend to be fractured at lower number of cycles when the specimens are subjected to higher ratio of fatigue load. On the other hand, the fatigue strength was improved by mixing the wood flours into the PP. Higher weight fraction of wood flours can exhibit higher fatigue strength. Regarding the specimens with single and double extrusion processes through the single screw extruder machine, the dispersion state of wood flours in the latter was clearly better than the former, as shown later. These specimens are denoted as 30% WF/PP-1, 50% WF/PP-1 and 30% WF/PP-2, 50% WF/PP-2. As seen in Fig. 3, both WF/PP-2 specimens indicate higher fatigue properties compared to the WF/PP-1 specimens.

Fig. 3 S-N diagram for neat PP and WPCs specimens.

3.3 Surface observation

Figure 4 shows an arbitrary cross-sectional area of 30% WF/PP and 50% WF/PP specimens at single and double extrusion processes. The clustered wood flours are clearly seen in Figure 4(a), of which the largest cluster size is approximately 600 μ m in length. When high amount of PP was added to the highly dense wood-PP pellets (*master-batch* pellet contains approximately 70wt.% of wood flour), it is hard for the pellets to disband and scatter uniformly through the PP matrix in a short time. That is to say, the duration of single extrusion to mix the materials is considerably short, resulting in the formation of clustered wood flours. Unlike 30% WF/PP-1 specimens, 50% WF/PP-1 causes the formation of smaller clusters because of less amount of PP mixed with *master-batch* pellets, as shown in Fig. 4(b). Figures 4(c) and 4(d) show arbitrary cross-sections of 30% WF/PP-2 and 50% WF/PP-2 specimens. The wood flours were distributed at more favorable distribution level, leading to the good results for both tensile and fatigue tests.

As for metal-based materials, the fatigue behaviors from the fatigue fracture surface are much easier to recognize compared to the WPCs material. This is because, the fatigue damage process that are commonly found at the fracture surface of the metallic materials, such as crack nucleation area, crack propagation path, striation and so on, are somehow almost impossible to mark out at WPCs surface. Consequently, the fatigue behaviors of this material are difficult to be characterized. As shown in Figs. 5(a)-(d), the fatigue fracture surface of each type WPCs specimen exhibits non-specific patterns of fatigue behavior, independent of the number of extrusion or the weight fraction of the wood flour. Furthermore, the similar morphology was observed independent of fatigue load levels. As mentioned

above, the fatigue behavior is commonly traced at the fracture surface, but it is definitely difficult to clarify the trace in detail.

Fig. 4 Observation of cross-sections of (a) 30% WF/PP-1, (b) 50% WF/PP-1, (c) 30% WF/PP-2 and (d) 50% WF/PP-2 specimens.

An observation method was set up in order to understand the fatigue behavior of WPCs specimens. Firstly, a short-length video was taken at certain time before the specimen reached to fracture. The whitened area that was formed after a certain number of cyclic loading and fatigue load level was observed from the area nearby the side surface of the specimen, as indicated by the arrow of Fig. 6(a). After that, the whitened area extended toward the center of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 6(a), and finally the specimen was fractured. The horizontal plane of fatigue fracture surface of the specimens was then examined by 3D Laser Measuring Microscope to confirm the difference of physical and morphology between the area close to the crack initiation and the remote area from the initiation point. From Fig. 6(b), it is understood that the fatigue fracture surface of WPCs specimen contains different surface morphologies and color. One is a relatively flat surface, and another shows an uneven surface. And the former consists of the whitened area, and the latter is a brown area which is the WPCs' original color. That is to say, the former surface is corresponding to the stable crack propagation area

despite the non-opening and the latter is to the unstable one. Although it is estimated that the whitened area is caused by crazing of PP matrix, this area behaves as a crack.

Fig. 5 Fatigue fracture surface of each type of WPCs specimens at 70% of fatigue load: (a) 30% WF/PP-1, (b) 50% WF/PP-1, (c) 30% WF/PP-2 and (d) 50% WF/PP-2.

The good interfacial adhesion of matrix-fillers increases the deformation resistance of the material, but at the specimen surface, PP matrix tends to deform largely compared to the inside because of free surface. This leads to occurrences of the plastic deformation or micro-cracks for PP matrix surround the wood flours, while internal PP matrix is restricted in deformation and expansion stress occurs without crack extension, especially at the area nearby the plastic deformation or micro-cracks area. Expansion stress occurring in the matrix causes micro-voids and followed by fibrillation of PP molecular chains. We consider this is the mechanism of whitening, i.e. crazing, at the fatigue damage process. Moreover, crazing extends into the polymer-rich area in between wood flours, under cyclic loading. Even if wood flours exist ahead the tip of the crazes, crazing extends without involving wood flours, because the flours adhere at the root of fibrillation due to the strong bonding. Thus, at the craze extension area, many traces of PP matrix fibrillation are observed, as shown in Fig. 7(a), and also some wood flours are recognized. This aspect is clearly different from the unstable propagation area illustrated in Fig. 7(b).

Fig. 6 (a) Fatigue crack initiation area (indicates by arrow) before the specimen ruptured at certain number of cyclic loading; (b) fatigue fracture surface contains different morphologies and color.

Fig. 7 Fatigue fracture surface at (a) nearby the crack initiation area and (b) unstable propagation area.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, different weight fractions of wood flours in WPCs specimens were fabricated in order to investigate the influence of wood flours weight fraction on the tensile and fatigue properties. From this study, the tensile and fatigue properties of WPCs were enhanced by compounding the wood fibers up to 50 wt.%. The good interfacial adhesion between the wood flour and the PP matrix, as a result from the addition of coupling agent MAPP to the compound, plays an important role towards enhancing the properties of WPCs material. In addition, the dispersion of wood flours inside the PP matrix was improved through the double extrusion process. From the fatigue fracture surface observation, it was concluded that the fatigue damage mechanism of WPCs specimen was initially formed by a plastic deformation or micro-crack at specimen's surface area and then continued to bring the crazing process toward the inside of the specimen until finally a catastrophic failure occurred.

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